

Nostalgia for Self-Identity in Elizabeth Bowen's *The Little Girls*

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Abstract:

Elizabeth Bowen is a novelist of outstanding creativity and influences of Henry James, Jane Austen and Virginia Woolf. The novel *The Little Girls* is one of her mature novels dealing with memory, childhood and search of identity in the past. The nostalgia for self-identity of Elizabeth Bowen is under the surface of this novel. This novel has a close relevance to Bowen's early memories. This paper throws light on the life of three aging ladies which reflects their search of identity by going back to the past mentally and remaining in the present physically. Dinah, Clare and Sheila are three women but Dinah is more interested than other two women as far as returning to the past and remaining in the present. Dinah is self-involved and likes to live in her own world. In this novel, Bowen describes many incidents of past and present life of three women to reflect their mental condition.

Keywords: Search, Identity, Past, Memory, Childhood, Emotional deprivation, Funeral ceremony, Friendship, Present, Cathartic effect.

Introduction:

Elizabeth Bowen is a novelist of outstanding creativity who began writing in 1930s and continued till 1970s. She is greatly influenced by Henry James, Jane Austen and Virginia Woolf in the treatment of themes and style of writing. Her novels express unique views on the quality of life during the century both in England and Ireland. Being an Anglo-Irish by birth, Bowen maintains a sense of unique detachment in her views and analysis of English life in her writings. The novel *The Little Girls* is one of her mature novels written at the age of 60 published in 1964. It is one of Bowen's quality texts dealing about memory, childhood and nostalgia for self-identity for the past living in the present. In this novel, the past is ever present and where fate can act very easily upon its inhabitants.

Search of Identity and its Relevance in the Novel:

Every person has his own personality. One possesses one's identity which is nothing but self-identity. It is a natural trait of every human being to search one's identity in one or other way. In the same way, Elizabeth Bowen searches her identity in her novels. *The Little Girls* is one of them. As Bowen grew older, her sense of isolation increased and the complexity is seen in her works like *The Little Girls* and *Eva Trout*. In her life, she experienced unusual mixture of aristocratic privilege and emotional deprivation; she was deprived of natural privilege like mother's funeral and so could not mourn naturally. Her subsequent moves from Ireland to Kent (England) raised the question of her own nation and her identity also. Her early life taught her to love places and things more than people and preserve memories of her past childhood which are evoked at the age of sixty and create a

sense of isolation. All this made Elizabeth Bowen to search her identity in her novel *The Little Girls*.

Reflection of nostalgia for self-identity in *The Little Girls*:

This research paper throws light on the life of three aging English ladies especially Dinah who try to search for her identity in past but all in vain. Clare and Sheila are forced by a chance call of Dinah to evocate the past but they are happy to live in the present and satisfied too. Sheila Arthworth is a well-settled, middle-class woman at Somerset. Clare is a self-made business woman. She has excelled in handling her Mopsie Pye shops. They are the product of their times and perfectly represent middle class society in England. Dinah, the protagonist of the novel is sixty-year-old woman with extraordinary beauty. Her youthful appearance shows that life has not much affected her. She is a widow living a lonely life at Applegate. Being a woman, very recently she has been engaged in the task of burying objects in the cave. So that future generation will be able to reconstruct her race from those remnants. Dinah and Frank are burying some objects at the outset of the novel which appears to be an archaeological enterprise. This suggests that Dinah has some purpose in this task. She has her own view of history. Dinah's deliberate burying of 'time capsule' is purely personal and purposeful. In this context John Coates remarks:

'To bury evidence is necessarily to filter and select one is choosing what one considers important about oneself or one's time and obviously, the choice may be entirely wrong. If there is an intention to dig up the buried objects later, then the burying becomes the making of an appointment to meet oneself, raising acutely the question of self-knowledge.' (John Coates: Winter 92: 6)

When Dinah's friend Mrs. Coral puts the question who's going to seal it up? She suddenly

realizes that she is repeating the past experience. She becomes obsessed with the desire to find her long-lost friends of St. Agatha's School. Dinah spends money worth £100 for newspaper advertisement. This shows Dinah's keen interest in her friends and her task of burial. Dinah's burying of expressive objects reveals that they are means for times to come to comprehend personalities. As a child, Bowen could not participate in her mother's funeral ceremony. So she buried a biscuit tin containing some cryptic writing. This suppression of not watching the funeral ceremony is found in this novel too. The little girls bury the coffer with objects and hence Bowen compensates for that exclusion in past. Dinah too tries to identify herself with past activity of burying coffer and wants her friends to be a part of this interesting enterprise to reopen the coffer.

Dinah represents the contemporary middle-class society. The impercipient cave symbolizes Dinah's personality as loving, exuberant and confused. Being very close to her mother in her childhood, Dinah retains the memories of her mother. Mrs. Piggott loves China which is recollected by Dinah. Mrs. Piggott dwells on the emotional value of objects and helps to maintain a sense of continuity and almost a thing of identity. Dinah fails to understand that her friends Clare and Sheila have a life of their own. They are purely practical in nature. Both of them are not interested in Dinah's enterprise. Her constant ringing forces them to participate in this task.

Clare's Disturbance is expressed:

'To have met again has been very nice. But we cannot keep in- ing and outing every two days. We have lives to live.' (Elizabeth Bowen: 1999: 7)

Dinah is always in her own world and is not a product of her time like her friends. Time

affects Sheila and Clare. Dinah is always protected from the beginning of her childhood till present. When Dinah and Clare go to the cottage in this absence of her nature and her feeling of insecurity in her own home. When Dinah and friends find out the coffer empty which shocks Dinah where as her friends are normal. She feels completely defeated when Clare accuses Dinah for a selfish nature and calls her enchantress child.

She goes in a trauma. Her friends nurse her and show the due affection when needed. Clare goes back to her childhood days when Frank reinforces in her mind. She understands the depth and truth of childhood friendship. Looking at sleeping Dinah she remarks:

‘We were entrusted to one another in the days which matured. Clare thought. Entrusted to one another by chance, not choice. Chance and its agents time and place. Chance is better than choice.’(Elizabeth Bowen: 1999: 8)

This also means that trust between them is violated by Dinah purposely to unite her friends for only one task to reopen the coffer. Friendship is to be based on love and understanding. The empty coffer also symbolizes that Dinah fails to understand her friends. At the end, Clare realizes that Dinah fears failure of her task to preserve the past. This also means that past is irrevocable but Dinah’s way of handling and preserving the past is completely wrong.

On the other hand, Dinah’s friends Sheila and Clare are perfectly worldly women. They live in the present and face all oddities of life. So, they identify their life with present situation. When Dinah wants to get in touch with them it appears to them eccentric and seems to threaten their personality and reputation affecting their

identities. They do not cling to past and are happy to live in present. The call of Dinah’s voice is a knock and blow to their own status and identity. Sheila and Clare’s artificiality symbolize that two women are frightened and are conscious of the world around them, without confidence they defend themselves by costly dresses and purchases. They hide their identity. The success of Mopsie Pye Shop also suggests the rootlessness and restlessness of modern man.

Conclusion:

Elizabeth Bowen has tried to reflect the lives of three friends; Dinah plays a major role and is the cause of many incidents in the past and present life of three friends. Dinah nostalgia for self-identity in past which tortured her. One should live in the present rather than go back to past. Dinah tries to struggle against the sense of loss in an unconventional way of life review in which Bowen participated by proxy. Bowen herself experienced a cathartic effect from completing the novel.

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